

Article

The Uncertainty of Economic Policy: A Hinder for Financial Sustainability?

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Abstract: *Creating a favorable and robust national financial ecosystem represents a pivotal objective for China during its new phase of development. This article employs principal component analysis to quantify trends in financial vulnerability, condition, stability, pressure, and development, collectively serving as indicators of financial market performance. Following this, the article delves deeper into the influence of uncertainty in economic policy on financial market operations by leveraging the SVAR model. The research concludes that an increase in economic policy uncertainty (EPU) initially exacerbates the fragility of the financial market, causing significant volatility and impacting its stability negatively. However, China's financial market possesses a self-regulation mechanism that gradually mitigates and transforms this impact over time. Notably, a positive shock to EPU can alleviate financial pressure in the short term by temporarily suppressing the vitality of the market. In addition, the overall rise in EPU hinders financial development. In summary, despite the market's self-regulatory capacity, heightened EPU still hinders financial sustainability in China. Based on this research, it is recommended that China should strengthen policy coordination and predictability to promote financial sustainability.*

Keywords: *Financial sustainability; Economic policy uncertainty; Principal component analysis; SVAR model.*

1. Introduction

The primary objective of this article is to investigate the impact of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) on financial sustainability in China. By observing real-world practices, we can gain a deeper understanding of the concept of economic policy uncertainty. When the government regulates economic operations through the formulation and implementation of specific economic policies, and as the economic situation becomes increasingly intricate, the government often intensifies its efforts to steer the economy (Bose et al., 2024; Choi and Park, 2024). This, in turn, magnifies the scale of adjustments made to economic policies (Kayani et al., 2024). Subjectively, market participants may encounter difficulties in accurately forecasting the direction and magnitude of these policies, resulting in an exacerbation of economic policy uncertainty, as noted by Mo et al. (2024). In the interconnected global economy, economic policies play a pivotal role in shaping market dynamics, investor behavior, and financial sustainability. Economic policy uncertainty can create volatility in financial markets, making it difficult for investors to predict future trends and returns (Liu et al., 2023; Gaies et al., 2024). This unpredictability would lead to a decrease in investor confidence, which in turn could reduce capital flows into financial markets and decrease the willingness of businesses to invest in long-term projects (Rehman et al., 2021; Man et al., 2024; Marques and Pinto, 2024). Such a scenario would hinder the growth of the financial sector and the broader economy, thereby compromising financial sustainability.

Moreover, uncertainty in economic policies would affect the pricing of financial assets (Bouri et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024). When policies are unclear or frequently changing, it becomes challenging for market participants to accurately assess the risk and return profiles of various investments (Mohammed et al., 2023). Such disruptions can undermine the stability of financial markets and the sustainability of financial institutions. Additionally, frequent changes in policies can make it difficult for regulators to keep pace with market developments and ensure the stability and resilience of the financial system. Therefore, understanding how EPU affects financial markets is crucial for policymakers, investors, and regulators seeking to foster a resilient and stable financial environment.

China, as the world's second-largest economy (Xue et al., 2024; Yue et al., 2024), offers a unique and compelling lens through which to examine the intricate relationship between EPU and financial sustainability. The nation's rapid economic growth, coupled with ongoing structural transformations and reforms, has led to a significant increase in the complexity and inter-connectedness of its financial markets (Cheng et al., 2024; Dinkneh et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024). This evolution has made China's financial system not only a critical component of the domestic economy but also a pivotal player in the global financial landscape. Thereupon, the impact of EPU on China's financial system is thus a matter of considerable concern (Huang and Luk, 2020; Xiao et al., 2024; Zhou and Chen, 2024). By focusing specifically on China, this study aims to delve into the nuanced ways in which EPU affects financial markets in a large, emerging economy. By doing so, the study hopes to provide valuable insights that can inform similar analyses in other countries, particularly those undergoing similar economic and structural transformations. Through examining China's experience, policymakers, investors, and researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with managing EPU in an emerging market context. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on financial sustainability in the face of economic policy uncertainties.

This research makes several innovative contributions to the existing body of knowledge in the field of financial markets and EPU. First, it introduces the use of principal component analysis (PCA) as a method to quantify and assess trends in financial vulnerability, condition, stability, pressure, and development. By employing PCA, the study offers a comprehensive and nuanced evaluation of financial market performance, which goes beyond traditional, more simplistic metrics. This approach not only provides a broader perspective on the overall health of financial markets but also allows for a deeper understanding of how EPU influences various facets of the financial system in a quantifiable manner. Secondly, the research leverages the powerful structural vector auto-regressive (SVAR) model to analyze the dynamic and intricate relationship between EPU and financial market performance. By utilizing this advanced econometric tool, the study is able to shed light on the temporal and causal effects of EPU on financial markets. This analysis reveals how changes in EPU over time impact financial market behavior and outcomes, offering valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms through which EPU exerts its influence. Thirdly, the insights offered by this research are valuable for policymakers and regulators who are tasked with promoting financial stability and sustainability in an increasingly uncertain economic environment. By providing a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how EPU impacts financial markets, this study equips policymakers with the knowledge and tools needed to develop effective strategies for mitigating the adverse effects of EPU and fostering a more resilient and sustainable financial system.

The structure of this research paper is outlined as follows: In Section 2, we compile and critically evaluate pertinent literature. Sections 3 and 4 describe, respectively, the empirical methods employed and the dataset used in our investigation. Section 5 delves into the empirical findings. Lastly, Section 6 summarizes the key conclusions and presents strategic suggestions.

2. Literature Review

Existing research has explored the impact of EPU on financial market from various perspectives, yielding differentiated conclusions. From the perspective of financial assets, Mohammed et al. (2023) suggest that EPU-induced shocks to financial assets are mediated through investor sentiments and are generally perceived in both uptrend and downtrend market conditions. Cheng et al. (2024) show that increased EPU prompts a flight to safety behavior, boosting bond liquidity. Consequently, this leads to decreased financing costs and narrower credit spreads. This phenomenon is particularly evident among

municipal corporations with higher credit ratings and in the aftermath of default events. Liu (2024) indicates that there is a direct correlation between EPU and the risk associated with credit asset allocation. Specifically, EPU amplifies the risk of credit asset allocation by hindering the flow of cross-border capital.

From the perspective of financial cycle, Che et al. (2023) notice that post-2010, a shock in EPU has triggered a decline in China's financial cycle and exerted a more pronounced indirect influence compared to any other time period. Liu et al. (2023) observe that China's financial and business cycles, both in the short and medium term, have been undergoing a recovery. However, the long-term elements continue to be in a contractionary phase, partly attributed to the rising EPU. Gonzalez et al. (2024) underscore the crucial impact of financial uncertainty in the U.S. on shaping global business cycles. Elevated uncertainties within the U.S. financial sector adversely influence global economic activity by hindering credit availability and stock prices, thereby restricting funding prospects for businesses and households across the globe.

From the perspective of financial risks, Duan et al. (2022) underline that an increase in EPU tends to enhance banks' contributions to systemic risk. And this effect operates via the risk associated with bank leverage and asset risk. Additionally, certain formal banking regulations (such as the regulatory framework) and informal institutions (such as national culture) can mitigate this effect. Muhammad et al. (2024) reveal that the rising uncertainty surrounding economic policies would lead to a substantial increase in the macro leverage ratio, thereby exacerbating financial risks. This phenomenon poses significant challenges to the sustainability of the financial system. Tang and Yang (2024) suggest that EPU is inversely related to financial risk. They uncover a potential economic mechanism through which corporate investment decisions mediate the negative correlation between monetary policy uncertainty and corporate financial risk.

From the perspective of financial stability, Phan et al. (2020) prove that a standard deviation increase in EPU leads to a decline in financial stability ranging from 2.66% to 7.26% of its average value across the sample. This detrimental effect of EPU on financial stability is more significant in countries characterized by higher competition, lower regulatory capital, and smaller financial systems. Kishwar et al. (2023) highlight that EPU has a notable adverse impact on overall financial stability (assessed using the Z-score) but a marked positive influence on financial stability within the banking sector of most developed economies (indicated by the non-performing loans). Wu et al. (2024) confirm that uncertainty in economic policy undermines financial stability within specific segments of the data distribution. Furthermore, the results highlight the varying degrees of asymmetry in this relationship among different countries.

In summary, there exists a notable gap in the specific research dedicated to understanding the ramifications of EPU on diverse indicators that gauge the functioning of financial markets. The academic community widely acknowledges that the unpredictability surrounding economic policies can exert a profound influence on the operation of macro-financial systems. Consequently, delving into the precise impact of EPU on various representative indicators that reflect financial sustainability holds considerable significance. This research not only holds academic value but also carries practical ramifications for maintaining financial sustainability and guiding policy formulation.

3. Methodology

The traditional vector auto-regressive (VAR) model is both practical and effective, finding widespread application across numerous fields. However, it possesses a limitation in that it cannot measure the correlation between current variables, instead burying these current correlations within the correlation structure of the error term, thereby rendering them inexplicable (Sims, 1986). In response to this limitation, this article introduces the structural vector auto-regressive (SVAR) model for empirical analysis. This model encompasses the current impact between variables within its framework, thereby aligning more closely with the prevalent economic and financial environment. The setting of the SVAR model in this article is as the following formula.

$$AY_t = F_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + F_s Y_{t-s} + \mu_t \quad t = s + 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

where Y_t is an observable vector of $k \times 1$ dimension, Y_{t-1}, \dots, Y_{t-s} are the lag vectors of Y_t . F_1, \dots, F_s refer to the coefficient matrices. μ_t measures the structural shock, satisfying $\mu_t \sim N(0, \Sigma)$, Σ is revealed as follows:

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \sigma_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Assuming that structural shock must obey recursive identification in SVAR model, indicating that A could be expressed as Equation (3).

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ a_{21} & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ a_{k1} & \dots & a_{k,k-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Then, Equation (1) can be written as follow:

$$Y_t = X_t' \beta + A^{-1} \sum \varepsilon_t \quad t = s+1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

where $X_t' = I_k \otimes (Y_{t-1}', \dots, Y_{t-s}')$. β is a $k^2 s \times 1$ dimensional vector. $\varepsilon_t \sim N(0, I_k)$.

At the same time, to ensure the recognition of the formulated SVAR model, this paper proceeds to apply conditional limitations. When establishing these conditional limitations, it is crucial to take into account the economic foundations of the variables involved. Given the unique economic circumstances of China, this paper proposes the following hypotheses: EPU would exert an influence on the indicators of the current financial market performance, whereas these indicators will not exert mutual influences among themselves. Consequently, constraint conditions are derived, allowing for the derivation of the relationship between the structural disturbance term and the impact term of the structural vector autoregressive model presented in this paper.

4. Data

This paper selects data from January 2008 to December 2020 for analysis. On the one hand, we employ the China Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), constructed by Baker et al. (2016), as a measure of the unpredictability surrounding China's economic policies. Utilizing text mining techniques, it searches for specific keywords within the daily news reports of the South China Morning Post, a Hong Kong-based newspaper. With January 1995 serving as the baseline with a value of 100, subsequent monthly data is indexed to derive the final indicator, referred to as EPU. Currently, this indicator is the primary tool utilized by Chinese academics to investigate economic policy uncertainty. This indicator is taken from the Economic Policy Uncertainty Website, and the trend of EPU is shown in Figure 1. As depicted in the following figure, EPU has exhibited a notable upward trend since 2017, suggesting that the overall unpredictability of China's economic policies has gradually escalated. Various significant economic and political occurrences during this period, including the inclusion of the renminbi in the Special Drawing Rights (SDR) basket, adjustments to the Renminbi's intermediate pricing mechanism, and Trump's trade war, have all contributed to this increase in economic policy uncertainty. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 has a profound impact on China's economy, causing a sudden downturn in the economic situation, intensifying the uncertainty surrounding economic policies.

Figure 1. The trend of EPU

On the other hand, this article focuses on exploring the influence of EPU on financial market performance from five perspectives: financial vulnerability (FV), financial condition (FC), financial stability (FS), financial pressure (FP), and financial development (FD). The original data in these indices are sourced from the Wind Database. First, we construct these indices by establishing four comprehensive evaluation index systems. To be specific, FV serves as a metric to quantify the fragility level of financial system in China, and the evaluation indicators are revealed in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation indicators for FV

Comprehensive indicators	First level indicators	Secondary indicators	Attribute
Financial vulnerability (FV)	Financial leverage	Resident sector asset liability ratio	+
		Leverage ratio of non-financial sector enterprises	+
		Leverage ratio of government departments	+
		Financial sector leverage ratio	+
		Leverage ratio of the real economy sector	+
		Short term external debt to foreign exchange reserves ratio	+
	Financial real estate	Real estate loans	+
		Real estate GDP	+
		Residential price index	+
	National debt	Fiscal shortfall	+
		M2/GDP	+
		New loans	+

FC serves as an indicator for assessing the operational status of China’s financial system, and the evaluation indicators are revealed in Table 2.

Table 2. Evaluation indicators for FC

Comprehensive indicators	First level indicators	Secondary indicators	Attribute
Financial condition (FC)	Interest rate conditions	Treasury bond yield	+
		Lending rate	+
		Rediscount rate	+
		Bill financing interest rate	+
		Housing loan interest rate	+
		Non-performing loan interest rate	+

	Capital market conditions	Interbank offered Rate	-
		Stock market volatility	-
		Stock market price to earnings ratio	+
		Fluctuations in housing prices	+
		Treasury bond index rose and fell	+
		The rise and fall of corporate bond index	+
		Futures trading volume year-on-year	+
		The rise and fall of fund indices	+

FS, according to the European Central Bank, denotes a condition where financial institutions, financial markets, and market infrastructures operate soundly and stably, possess the resilience to withstand various risk shocks, and do not impair the efficiency of transforming savings into investments. Table 3 presents the evaluation indicators.

Table 3. Evaluation indicators for FS

Comprehensive indicators	First level indicators	Secondary indicators	Attribute	
Financial stability (FS)	Economic operation status	Economic sentiment index	+	
		GDP growth rate	+	
		Monetary and quasi monetary M2 growth rates	-	
		Future price expectation index for urban depositors	-	
	Financial operation status	Financial institution	Financial institutions increase RMB loans in the current month	-
			Non-performing loan ratio	-
			Interbank offered rate	+
			Deposit loan ratio	+
			The People's Bank of China's loan interest rate for financial institutions	+
		Financial market	Scale of social financing	-
			Debt market value/GDP	+
			Average price to earnings ratio of stocks	+
			National housing prosperity index	+
		Financial system	Real Renminbi effective exchange rate index	+
			M2/GDP	-
		International balance of payments situation	Foreign exchange reserve	+
	Foreign exchange reserves/external debt		+	
	Monthly trade balance		+	

FP refers to the impact of the changes and uncertainties within the financial market, as well as the anticipated losses incurred by financial institutions, on the overall financial system. Table 4 shows the evaluation indicators.

Table 4. Evaluation indicators for FP

Comprehensive indicators	First level indicators	Secondary indicators	Attribute
Financial pressure (FP)	Monetary market conditions	3-month interbank lending weighted interest rate	+
		3-month interest rate swap based on FR007	+

	Bond market conditions	Yield to maturity of one-year treasury bond	+
		Yield to maturity of five-year treasury bond	+
	Stock market conditions	The rise and fall of the Shanghai Composite Index	+
		Net ratio of Shanghai stock exchange	-
		Rolling P/E ratio of Shanghai Stock Exchange A-shares	-
	Foreign exchange market conditions	Real effective exchange rate index of Renminbi	-
		USD to RMB NDF	-
		Euro to RMB exchange rate	+
	Financial and real estate situation	Real estate industry GDP year-on-year growth rate	+
		Financial real estate price to book ratio	+
	Insurance market conditions	Insurance payout amount	-

FD encompasses the inherent vitality, operational capability, and growth potential of its entire financial system, providing a comprehensive reflection of the operational status of China’s financial market. Table 5 shows the evaluation indicators.

Table 5. Evaluation indicators for FD

Comprehensive indicators	First level indicators	Secondary indicators	Attribute
Financial development (FD)	The impact of financial development on economic development	M2	+
		GDP financial industry	+
	The impact on investment activities	Market value of the stock market	+
		Futures trading volume	+
		Bond financing amount	+
	The impact on production activities	Financial assets/total assets	+
		Net profit of commercial banks	+
	The impact on life	National housing prosperity index	+
		Total amount of securitized assets	+
		Domestic credit balance	+

Prior to analysis, the time series data for each variable is normalized to ensure uniformity in dimensions. Subsequently, this article utilizes Eviews 10 to perform seasonal tests on all indicators and applies Census-X12 seasonal adjustments to pertinent indicators, thereby mitigating the influence of seasonal factors. Furthermore, principal component analysis (PCA) is employed to reduce the weight of indicators. PCA, recommended by the IMF as one of the preferred dimensionality reduction methods, is renowned for its simplicity and directness (Moradi et al., 2024). It prevents the assignment of disproportionately high weights to specific variables due to factors such as inter-indicator correlation (Ren et al., 2024). Notably, discrepancies in data intervals may result in varying starting dates for different variables, hindering a comprehensive principal component analysis across all time intervals. To incorporate as much valuable information as possible into the dimensionality reduction analysis of each index, PCA is conducted separately for distinct time periods, followed by the synthesis of the first-order differences of them. This process integrates indices from different time periods into a unified index. After calculation, the trends of FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD are shown in the following graphs.

Figure 2. The trends of FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD

As evident from the aforementioned charts, the financial vulnerability index has been consistently ascending in recent times. This upward trajectory can be attributed to the rapid development of China’s financial industry, which is still in the process of establishing a comprehensive institutional framework. The immense growth potential of this industry serves as a significant driver for economy while also posing corresponding potential risks. In contrast, China’s financial condition index has generally exhibited a fluctuating downward trend in recent years. However, this decline does not necessarily reflect a deterioration in China’s investment environment. The selection of original indicators in this article primarily measures financial market conditions based on interest rate levels across various sectors. The overall downward trend in the curve underscores the gradual reduction in interest rates over the years, which, to some extent, signifies the optimization and vitality of the investment environment, as well as the economic recovery. Regarding financial stability, China’s financial stability has experienced a sharp decline since 2008, reaching its nadir in early 2009. It only fully recovered by the end of 2015. This underscores the profound impact of the 2008 financial crisis on China’s financial

market stability, which lingered for several years. In the first quarter of 2020, China's financial stability saw a dramatic drop due to the COVID-19 outbreak, significantly affecting the operation of the real economy and the stability of the financial market. However, as China actively addressed the pandemic, steadily promoted the resumption of work and production, and witnessed a gradual recovery in the real economy, China's financial stability also gradually improved. This indicates that the pandemic's impact on the economy was temporary, and the fundamental situation of long-term stability and improvement in China's economy remains unchanged. Moreover, the financial stress index has experienced fluctuations and a decline in recent years. With the continuous advancement of China's financial work and the ongoing improvement in financial governance over the past few years, the pressure on the financial market should continue to ease. Additionally, China's financial development index has consistently shown a stable upward trend, confirming the rapid development of the financial industry over the years.

5. Empirical Analyses

In order to further explore the impact of economic policy uncertainty on financial market performance in China, this paper introduces the SVAR model to explore this issue. In empirical analysis, monthly observations of time series data frequently exhibit monthly cyclic changes, which can often obscure the underlying economic trends. Consequently, seasonal adjustments are often necessary prior to analysis. The five indicators utilized in this article to assess financial market operations are derived through principal component analysis, and the original data has undergone seasonal adjustment before being subjected to this analysis, rendering subsequent seasonal adjustments unnecessary. Therefore, prior to analysis, this article initially subjects EPU to seasonal adjustment, with the descriptive statistical results of the adjusted data presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics

	EPU	FV	FC	FS	FP	FD
Average value	2.797	0.074	-0.035	0.009	-0.021	0.173
Median	1.964	0.016	0.004	-0.011	0.004	0.092
Maximum value	232.837	1.950	1.670	1.914	0.815	1.264
Minimum value	-251.148	-0.968	-1.752	-1.449	-1.084	-0.568
Standard deviation	57.465	0.379	0.485	0.407	0.322	0.279
Skewness	0.167	1.961	-0.504	1.008	-0.460	1.489
Kurtosis	7.908	10.905	5.164	9.842	3.846	6.314

According to Table 1, the mean values of these variables, which are 2.797, 0.074, -0.035, 0.009, -0.021, and 0.173 respectively, indicate a tendency for these values to concentrate around these central tendencies. The notable disparities between their maximum and minimum values highlight the substantial fluctuations within these variables. The rightward asymmetry in the distributions of EPU, FV, FS, and FD, indicated by their positive skewness, suggests that their tails extend further to the right. FC and FP exhibit left-skewed distributions, where this left skewness fulfills the condition of smaller values occurring more frequently than the average, resulting in a shape of the distribution that leans to the left. In terms of kurtosis, EPU, FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD display a leptokurtic pattern, characterized by more pronounced peaks and thicker tails in comparison to standard normal distributions.

Given that several economic variables exhibit non-stationary properties, this paper employs the ADF test using Eviews to ensure that the analysis results are not compromised. The outcomes of the test, presented in Table 7, reveal that several time series data display non-stationarity, yet they become stationary after taking their first-order differences. Consequently, the subsequent analysis in this article will focus on the first-order differences of each variable individually.

Table 7. Descriptive statistics

Variables	ADF statistics	P-values	conclusion
EPU	-0.380	0.908	Non-stationary
First-order difference of EPU	-14.093 ***	0.000	Stationary

FV	-0.165	0.939	Non-stationary
First order difference of FV	-5.569 ***	0.000	Stationary
FC	-1.850	0.355	Non-stationary
First order difference of FC	-14.176 ***	0.000	Stationary
FS	-1.239	0.657	Non-stationary
First order differential of FS	-7.800 ***	0.000	Stationary
FP	-2.179	0.215	Non-stationary
First order difference of FP	-9.486 ***	0.000	Stationary
FD	-0.903	0.785	Non-stationary
First order difference of FD	-3.345 **	0.015	Stationary

To ascertain the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship among various variables, this paper adopts the Johansen cointegration test method to perform cointegration assessments. The results of these tests are presented in Tables 8 and 9.

Table 8. Results of trace statistics test

The number of cointegration relationships exists	Characteristic values	Trace statistics	At a significance level of 5%	Probability
There is no cointegration relationship	0.409	223.961	95.754	0.000
Up to 1 cointegration relationship	0.355	145.151	69.819	0.000
Up to 2 cointegration relationships	0.212	79.262	47.856	0.000
Up to 3 cointegration relationships	0.134	43.474	29.797	0.001
Up to 4 cointegration relationships	0.115	21.886	15.495	0.005
Up to 5 cointegration relationships	0.024	3.577	3.842	0.059

Table 9. Statistical test results of maximum eigenvalue

The number of cointegration relationships exists	Characteristic values	Maximum eigenvalue	At a significance level of 5%	Probability
There is no cointegration relationship	0.409	78.810	40.078	0.000
Up to one cointegration relationship	0.355	65.888	33.877	0.000
Up to 2 cointegration relationships	0.212	35.789	27.584	0.000
Up to 3 cointegration relationships	0.134	21.588	21.132	0.001
Up to 4 cointegration relationships	0.115	18.309	14.265	0.005
Up to 5 cointegration relationships	0.024	3.577	3.8415	0.059

Based on the results of the Johansen cointegration test mentioned above, it is evident that the *p*-values associated with the null hypotheses, which suggest “no cointegration relationship”, “at most 1 cointegration relationship”, “at most 2 cointegration relationships”, “at most 3 cointegration relationships”, and “at most 4 cointegration relationships”, are either extremely close to 0 or exactly 0. This implies that, at a significance level of 5%, all these hypotheses are rejected. Consequently, we conclude that there are precisely five cointegration relationships among the six variable time series. From this observation, we infer that there exists a long-term stable equilibrium relationship between the

EPU, FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD. Hence, it is feasible to construct the SVAR model using these six time series data.

Prior to estimation, the potential occurrence of multicollinearity among variables due to overlapping indicators is taken into consideration. To address this, Stata is employed to conduct multicollinearity tests on each variable. The results indicate a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of 2.4, which is significantly less than 10, suggesting that multicollinearity is not an issue. Prior to establishing a SVAR model, it is essential to determine the optimal lag order for the model, as outlined in Table 10. Given that the data selected for regression in this study is monthly, we have chosen a lag length of 4 periods as the optimal choice for the SVAR model.

Table 10. Selection of optimal lag order

Number of lag periods	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	NA	0.110	14.819	14.941	14.868
1	202.742	0.042	13.860	14.715	14.207 *
2	89.697	0.035	13.681	15.267	14.325=
3	82.569	0.030	13.525	15.845	14.468
4	64.444 *	0.030 *	13.487 *	16.538	14.727
5	48.506	0.032	13.559	17.342	15.096
6	40.316	0.038	13.682	18.198	15.517

This article employs the Granger causality test to examine the causal relationship between EPU and various variables related to financial market performance (FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD). The outcomes of this test are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Granger causality test results

Null hypothesis	F statistical values	Probability	Inspection results
EPU is not a Granger cause of FV	2.918 *	0.0572	refuse
EPU is not a Granger cause of FC	2.862 *	0.0603	refuse
EPU is not a Granger cause of FS	4.024 **	0.0199	refuse
EPU is not a Granger cause of FP	2.325	0.1013	Do not refuse
EPU is not a Granger cause of FD	1.098	0.3361	Do not refuse

As illustrated in Table 11, the results of the Granger causality test reveal that EPU serves as a Granger cause for FV, FC, nad FS. However, it does not act as a Granger cause for the FP and FD. Statistically, fluctuations in EPU have a direct impact on FV, FC, nad FS. This article proceeds to delve into the evolving relationships among various variables through impulse response analysis.

Based on the outcomes of the SVAR analysis, this article constructs an orthogonal impulse response function to examine the dynamic interaction effects of a unit change in the disturbance term of EPU on itself, FV, FC, FS, FP, and FD. The results of this analysis are presented below.

Figure 3. Impulse response results

As illustrated in Figure 3(a), regarding the influence of the disturbance term of EPU on itself, it exhibits the strongest positive impact in the initial period, progressively diminishing until it nearly converges to 0 by the eighth period. Economic behavior often exhibits temporal inertia, implying that the current economic state may be influenced by its past state. But as time passes, this influence tends to diminish.

As depicted in Figure 3(b), when a positive impact is applied to EPU, it initially exhibits a noticeable positive influence on FV during the first period. This suggests that an increase in EPU, at least initially, tends to exacerbate the vulnerability of the financial market. However, this effect does not persist; rather, it reverses to a negative influence in the second period. By the seventh period, the impact of EPU on FV has nearly converged to zero, indicating that the initial positive effect has been largely offset by subsequent negative effects. Initially, the surge in EPU amplifies the sensitivity and instability of the financial market, potentially leading to heightened risks and vulnerabilities. This is because EPU often reflects changes in government policies, economic outlooks, and market expectations, all of which can create uncertainty and volatility in the financial markets. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that China's financial market possesses a certain degree of self-regulatory capacity. This means that, over time, the market is able to gradually dissipate and transform the negative impact of EPU. The market's self-regulatory mechanisms, such as risk management, diversification, and liquidity adjustments, help to mitigate the adverse effects of EPU and restore stability.

As illustrated in Figure 3(c), applying a positive impact to EPU generally exerts a positive influence on FC. It further validates that an escalation in EPU tends to elevate interest rates, which in turn dampens investment activities. To be specific, when businesses and investors perceive a high level of uncertainty, they often become more cautious and reluctant to commit to new investments. This cautiousness leads to a decrease in demand for funds, which then puts upward pressure on interest rates as lenders seek to compensate for the increased risk. However, it's worth noting that the impact of EPU on FC is not static. As the figure suggests, the influence may change over time, reflecting the dynamic nature of financial markets and the economy.

As depicted in Figure 3(d), the introduction of a positive impact on EPU initially results in a negative effect on FS, characterized by notable volatility. This volatility underscores the complex and dynamic

nature of financial markets when confronted with shifts in EPU. However, it also signals a broader trend, China's financial market has acquired substantial resilience over the years through comprehensive governance efforts. This resilience manifests in the market's increasingly robust ability to address and absorb external shocks. Moreover, the gradual mitigation of the negative impact over time indicates that China's financial market is not only resilient but also has the capacity to learn and adapt to new conditions. This evolving resilience is crucial for maintaining financial stability and ensuring the smooth functioning of the economy.

As illustrated in Figure 3(e), when a positive impact is imparted to EPU, it results in an immediate alleviation of FP in the current period. This apparent relief, however, is linked to a temporary suppression of the vitality and dynamism within the financial market. The reasoning behind this phenomenon can be attributed to the cautious behavior adopted by market participants in response to heightened EPU. They may defer investments, tighten credit conditions, or adopt more conservative strategies, thereby reducing the immediate financial burden but at the cost of stifling market activity. Yet, it is crucial to acknowledge that this short-term mitigation of FP does not signify a comprehensive solution. On the contrary, an overall increase in EPU tends to amplify the operational pressure on the financial market in the broader sense. This is because heightened uncertainty clouds the economic outlook, making it challenging for market participants to make informed decisions. This, in turn, leads to increased volatility, reduced liquidity, and heightened risks, all of which exacerbate the operational challenges faced by financial institutions.

As depicted in Figure 3(f), the escalation in EPU exerts a mixed impact on FD, underscoring the significant impact that uncertainty in economic policies can have on the broader financial landscape. Higher levels of EPU tend to create an environment of caution and conservatism among investors, lenders, and other market participants, leading to a slowdown in financial activities and investments. When economic policies are subject to frequent changes and uncertainties, it becomes challenging for market participants to plan and make informed decisions, ultimately hindering financial growth and progress.

6. Conclusions and Suggestions

This article delves into the realm of economic policy uncertainty, utilizing its definition as a foundation to establish five comprehensive indicator systems aimed at assessing the performance of China's financial market. By employing principal component analysis on monthly data, the article quantifies various indices for China's financial market over the past 13 years, including financial vulnerability, condition, stability, pressure, and development. Following this meticulous measurement, the article further explores the intricate relationship between EPU and FV, FC, FS, FP, FD by leveraging the SVAR model. The findings indicate that an elevation in EPU initially intensifies the vulnerability of the financial market, leading to substantial fluctuations and undermining its stability. Nevertheless, China's financial market is endowed with a self-adjustment mechanism that progressively alleviates and redirects this impact over an extended period. It is noteworthy that a positive disruption in EPU can momentarily reduce financial pressure by temporarily dampening market dynamism. Furthermore, a general increase in EPU impedes financial growth. In essence, despite the market's innate regulatory abilities, heightened levels of EPU continue to pose obstacles to financial sustainability in China.

Based on these findings, this article proposes the following countermeasures and suggestions: First, enhancing policy coordination and predictability. China should prioritize the coordination of various economic policies to ensure consistency and coherence. Policy-making processes need to be transparent and predictable, as this can significantly reduce uncertainty in the market. Clear communication of policy intentions and objectives is crucial for stabilizing market expectations and minimizing volatility. By aligning policies and maintaining transparency, China can foster a more stable and predictable financial environment.

Second, strengthening financial market regulation and supervision. To maintain financial sustainability, China must improve its regulatory framework and enhance the capacity of financial regulators. This includes better monitoring and managing financial risks and ensuring that regulators can respond swiftly and effectively to emerging threats. Fostering a culture of compliance among financial institutions is

also essential for maintaining market integrity and preventing misconduct. By strengthening regulation and supervision, China can mitigate the risks associated with financial market operations.

Third, promoting financial inclusion and diversification. Expanding access to financial services to underserved segments of the population is crucial for promoting financial inclusion. Additionally, encouraging the development of diverse financial products and services can cater to the needs of different market participants and provide alternative investment options. Diversification not only enhances market resilience but also mitigates the impact of economic policy uncertainty by distributing risks more evenly across the financial system. By promoting financial inclusion and diversification, China can foster a more robust and inclusive financial ecosystem.

Fourth, promoting international cooperation and information sharing. Strengthening cooperation with international financial institutions and regulatory bodies is crucial for sharing best practices and addressing cross-border financial risks. China should actively participate in global financial governance structures to influence international financial rules and standards. Monitoring global economic trends and policies can help anticipate potential impacts on China's financial market and prepare for any necessary adjustments. By promoting international cooperation and information sharing, China can better navigate the global financial landscape and protect its financial system from external shocks.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Baker, S. R., Bloom, N., & Davis, S. J. (2016). Measuring economic policy uncertainty. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 4, 1593-1636.
2. Bose, S., Shams, S., Ali, S., Mamun, A. A., & Chang, M. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty, carbon emissions and firm valuation: International evidence. *The British Accounting Review*, 56(6), 101453.
3. Bouri, E., Gök, R., Gemici, E., & Kara, E. (2024). Do geopolitical risk, economic policy uncertainty, and oil implied volatility drive assets across quantiles and time-horizons? *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 93, 137-154.
4. Che, M., Zhu, Z., & Li, Y. (2023). Geopolitical risk and economic policy uncertainty: Different roles in China's financial cycle. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 90, 102867.
5. Cheng, T., Qiu, L., Lv, W., Yang, X., & Yang, G. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty and municipal corporate bonds credit spreads: Evidence from China. *Finance Research Letters*, 69, 106170-106170.
6. Choi, Y. M., & Park, K. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty and dividend policy: Insight from private firms. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 96, 103692.
7. Dinkneh, G. B., Jiang, Y., Miao, M., & Luo, X. (2024). The impacts of economic policy uncertainty, energy consumption, sustainable innovation, and quality of governance on green growth in emerging economies. *Energy & Environment*, 35(7), 3647-3672.
8. Duan, Y., Fan, X., & Wang, Y. (2022). Economic policy uncertainty and bank systemic risk: A cross-country analysis. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 75, 101828.
9. Gaies, B., Nakhli, M. S., & Sahut, J. M. (2024). Unravelling the complex interactions between sentiment of uncertainty and foreign capital flows: Evidence from Brazil and South Korea. *Economic Modelling*, 141, 106913.
10. Gonzalez, J. E. G., Garzon, J. H., & Uribe, J. M. (2024). US uncertainty shocks on real and financial markets: A multi-country perspective. *Economic Systems*, 48(3), 101180.

11. Huang, Y., & Luk, P. (2020). Measuring economic policy uncertainty in China. *China Economic Review*, 59, 101367.
12. Kayani, U., Hassan, M. K., Dejan, A., Khan, M., & Nawaz, F. (2024). Assessment of Economic Policy Uncertainty spillovers: A cross-border analysis of global and BRIC economies. *International Economics*, 179, 100530.
13. Kishwar, A., Hu, H., Yoong, L. C., & Du, J. (2023). Governance perspective and the effect of economic policy uncertainty on financial stability: evidence from developed and developing economies. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 56(3), 1971-2002.
14. Liu, B. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty, cross-border capital inflows and credit asset allocation risk. *Finance Research Letters*, 68, 105984.
15. Liu, D., Sun, W., Xu, L., & Zhang, X. (2023). Time-frequency relationship between economic policy uncertainty and financial cycle in China: Evidence from wavelet analysis. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 77, 101915.
16. Man, Y., Zhang, S., & He, Y. (2024). Dynamic risk spillover and hedging efficacy of China's carbon-energy-finance markets: Economic policy uncertainty and investor sentiment non-linear causal effects. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 93, 1397-1416.
17. Marques, G. O. L. C., & Pinto, M. G. F. (2024). Dynamics of persistence in Brazilian economic uncertainty, expectation, and confidence indexes. *Finance Research Letters*, 70, 106270.
18. Mo, T., Huangmei, M., Chen, H., Li, K., & Ouyang, Y. (2024). Tail risk spillovers between economic policy uncertainty and stock market returns: Evidence based on TENET approach. *Finance Research Letters*, 69, 106204.
19. Mohammed, K. S., Obeid, H., Oueslati, K., & Kaabia, O. (2023). Investor sentiments, economic policy uncertainty, US interest rates, and financial assets: Examining their interdependence over time. *Finance Research Letters*, 57, 104180.
20. Moradi, S., Nowroozi, A., Nezhad, M. A., Jalali, P., Khosravi, R., & Shahlai, M. (2024). A review on description dynamics and conformational changes of proteins using combination of principal component analysis and molecular dynamics simulation. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 183, 109245.
21. Muhammad, A., Saman, S., & Fiza, Q. (2024). Does economic policy uncertainty matter for a firm's leverage and speed of adjustment? *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 16(5), 1241-1258.
22. Phan, D. H. B., Iyke, B. N., Sharma, S. S., & Affandi, Y. (2020). Economic policy uncertainty and financial stability—Is there a relation? *Economic Modelling*, 94, 1018-1029.
23. Rehman, M. U., Sensoy, A., Eraslan, V., Shahzad, S. J. H., & Vo, X. V. (2021). Sensitivity of US equity returns to economic policy uncertainty and investor sentiments. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 57, 101392.
24. Ren, K., Wang, J., Su, H., Lu, Z., Lu, J., Fang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2024). Risk assessment of haze disaster in the Liaoning region based on ArcGIS and principal component analysis. *Ecological Indicators*, 168, 112757.
25. Sims, C. A. (1986). Are forecasting models usable for policy analysis? *The Quarterly Review*, 10, 2-16.
26. Tang, P., & Yang, W. (2024). Monetary policy uncertainty and financial risk: The mediating role of corporate investment. *Finance Research Letters*, 70, 106303.
27. Wu, J., Rasool, Z., Ali, S., & Nazar, R. (2024). Between policy swings and financial shockwaves: Asymmetric impact of economic policy uncertainty on financial stability in high-volatility nations. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 95, 102000.

28. Xiao, L., Zhao, L., & Zhu, Q. (2024). Host country economic policy uncertainty, trade openness and Chinese enterprise overseas investment. *International Review of Economics and Finance*, 96, 103566.
29. Xue, X., Wang, L., & Hu, N. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty and corporate social responsibility disclosure similarity: Evidence from China. *The British Accounting Review*, 56(5), 101305.
30. Yu, X., Li, Z., Lien, D., & Hu, J. (2024). Identifying crucial financial markets in the flows of cross-border capital – evidence from China’s financial risk network. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 96, 103670.
31. Yue, H., Wang, H., & Jin, P. (2024). Financial geographic structure and innovation quality: Evidence from Chinese firms amid economic policy uncertainty. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 84, 1370-1380.
32. Zhou, L., & Chen, P. (2024). Economic policy uncertainty and corporate cooperative research and development: Empirical evidence based on Chinese patent data. *Finance Research Letters*, 68, 105806.

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